

Overall Performance

Average Performance by SDG

SDG Dashboard and Trends

■ Major challenges
 ■ Significant challenges
 ■ Challenges remain
 ■ SDG achieved
 ■ Information unavailable
↓ Decreasing
 → Stagnating
 ↗ Moderately improving
 ↑ On track or maintaining SDG achievement
 ● Information unavailable

Statistical Performance Index

Number of Voluntary National Reviews (VNRs)

*Progress (in percentage points) is based on a set of 17 headline SDG indicators. Please see the methodology section for details.

SDG1 – No Poverty	Value	Year	Rating	Trend	SDG9 – Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	Value	Year	Rating	Trend	
Poverty headcount ratio at \$2.15/day (%)	1.1	2025	●	↑	Rural population with access to all-season roads (%)	99.0	2025	●	→	
Poverty headcount ratio at \$3.65/day (%)	5.5	2025	●	↑	Population using the internet (%)	55.9	2022	●	↑	
SDG2 – Zero Hunger					Mobile broadband subscriptions (per 100 population)	60.2	2023	●	↑	
Prevalence of undernourishment (%)	13.7	2022	●	→	Logistics Performance Index: Infrastructure Score (worst 1–5 best)	3.2	2023	●	→	
Prevalence of stunting in children under 5 years of age (%)	35.5	2020	●	→	The Times Higher Education Universities Ranking: Average score of top 3 universities (worst 0–100 best)	50.8	2025	●	↑	
Prevalence of wasting in children under 5 years of age (%)	18.7	2020	●	→	Articles published in academic journals (per 1,000 population)	0.2	2023	●	→	
Minimum dietary diversity among children aged 6–23 months (%)	23.6	2020	●	●	Expenditure on research and development (% of GDP)	0.6	2020	●	↓	
Prevalence of obesity, BMI ≥ 30 (% of adult population)	7.3	2022	●	→	Total patent applications by applicant's origin (per million population)	45.9	2023	●	→	
Human Trophic Level (best 2–3 worst)	2.3	2022	●	↓	SDG10 – Reduced Inequalities					
Cereal yield (tonnes per hectare of harvested land)	3.6	2022	●	↑	Gini coefficient	32.8	2021	●	↑	
Sustainable Nitrogen Management Index (best 0–1.41 worst)	0.8	2018	●	↗	Palma ratio	1.3	2021	●	↑	
Exports of hazardous pesticides (tonnes per million population)	0.9	2022	●	●	SDG11 – Sustainable Cities and Communities					
SDG3 – Good Health and Well-Being					Proportion of urban population living in slums (%)	41.4	2022	●	→	
Maternal mortality ratio (per 100,000 live births)	80.5	2023	●	↑	Annual mean concentration of PM2.5 (µg/m³)	47.3	2023	●	→	
Neonatal mortality rate (per 1,000 live births)	17.3	2023	●	↑	Access to improved water source, piped (% of urban population)	65.6	2022	●	↓	
Mortality rate, under-5 (per 1,000 live births)	27.7	2023	●	↑	Population with convenient access to public transport in cities (%)	69.8	2020	●	●	
Incidence of tuberculosis (per 100,000 population)	195.0	2023	●	→	SDG12 – Responsible Consumption and Production					
New HIV infections (per 1,000 uninfected population, all ages)	0.1	2023	●	●	Municipal solid waste (kg/capita/day)	0.4	2020	●	●	
Age-standardized death rate due to cardiovascular disease, cancer, diabetes, or chronic respiratory disease in adults aged 30 to 70 years (%)	23.6	2021	●	↓	Electronic waste that is not recycled (kg/capita)	2.9	2022	●	●	
Age-standardized death rate attributable to household air pollution and ambient air pollution (per 100,000 population)	139.0	2019	●	●	Production-based air pollution (DALYs per 1,000 population)	20.3	2024	●	↓	
Traffic deaths (per 100,000 population)	14.6	2021	●	→	Air pollution associated with imports (DALYs per 1,000 population)	0.5	2024	●	→	
Life expectancy at birth (years)	72.0	2023	●	→	Production-based nitrogen emissions (kg/capita)	22.1	2024	●	→	
Adolescent fertility rate (births per 1,000 females aged 15 to 19)	11.3	2020	●	→	Nitrogen emissions associated with imports (kg/capita)	1.8	2024	●	→	
Births attended by skilled health personnel (%)	89.4	2021	●	↑	Exports of plastic waste (kg/capita)	0.0	2023	●	↑	
Surviving infants who received 2 WHO-recommended vaccines (%)	91.0	2023	●	↑	SDG13 – Climate Action					
Universal health coverage (UHC) index of service coverage (worst 0–100 best)	63.3	2021	●	↗	CO ₂ emissions from fossil fuel combustion and cement production (tCO ₂ /capita)	2.2	2023	●	↓	
Subjective well-being (average ladder score, worst 0–10 best)	4.4	2024	●	↓	GHG emissions embodied in imports (tCO ₂ /capita)	0.4	2024	●	→	
SDG4 – Quality Education					CO ₂ emissions embodied in fossil fuel exports (tonnes/capita)	0.0	2023	●	●	
Participation rate in pre-primary organized learning (% of children aged 4 to 6)	94.4	2022	●	●	SDG14 – Life Below Water					
Net primary enrollment rate (%)	99.9	2024	●	↑	Mean area that is protected in marine sites important to biodiversity (%)	4.2	2023	●	→	
Lower secondary completion rate (%)	85.5	2023	●	→	Ocean Health Index: Clean Waters score (worst 0–100 best)	32.3	2024	●	→	
Literacy rate (% of population aged 15 to 24)	97.0	2023	●	↑	Fish caught from overexploited or collapsed stocks (% of total catch)	7.4	2018	●	→	
SDG5 – Gender Equality					Fish caught by trawling or dredging (%)	4.4	2019	●	↑	
Demand for family planning satisfied by modern methods (% of females aged 15 to 49)	77.5	2024	●	↑	Fish caught that are then discarded (%)	4.7	2019	●	↑	
Ratio of female-to-male mean years of education received (%)	72.5	2022	●	↗	Marine biodiversity threats embodied in imports (per million population)	0.0	2018	●	●	
Ratio of female-to-male labor force participation rate (%)	42.6	2024	●	→	SDG15 – Life on Land					
Seats held by women in national parliament (%)	13.8	2025	●	→	Mean area that is protected in terrestrial sites important to biodiversity (%)	6.3	2023	●	→	
SDG6 – Clean Water and Sanitation					Mean area that is protected in freshwater sites important to biodiversity (%)	8.3	2023	●	→	
Population using at least basic drinking water services (%)	93.3	2022	●	↗	Red List Index of species survival (worst 0–1 best)	0.67	2023	●	↓	
Population using at least basic sanitation services (%)	78.4	2022	●	↑	Permanent deforestation (% of forest area, 3-year average)	0.0	2023	●	→	
Freshwater withdrawal (% of available freshwater resources)	66.5	2022	●	→	Imported deforestation (m ² /capita)	0.9	2022	●	↑	
Anthropogenic wastewater that receives treatment (%)	19.2	2015	●	●	SDG16 – Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions					
Scarce water consumption embodied in imports (m ³ H ₂ O eq/capita)	128.2	2024	●	→	Homicides (per 100,000 population)	2.8	2022	●	↗	
SDG7 – Affordable and Clean Energy					Crime is effectively controlled (worst 0–1 best)	0.79	2023	●	↑	
Population with access to electricity (%)	99.2	2022	●	↑	Unsented detainees (% of prison population)	75.8	2022	●	↓	
Population with access to clean fuels and technology for cooking (%)	74.5	2022	●	↑	Birth registrations with civil authority (% of children under age 5)	89.1	2021	●	●	
CO ₂ emissions from fuel combustion per total electricity output (MtCO ₂ /TWh)	1.7	2023	●	→	Corruption Perceptions Index (worst 0–100 best)	38.0	2024	●	→	
Renewable energy share in total final energy consumption (%)	18.0	2021	●	↗	Children involved in child labor (%)	●	●	●	●	
SDG8 – Decent Work and Economic Growth					Exports of major conventional weapons (TIV constant million USD per 100,000 population)	0.0	2024	●	●	
Adjusted GDP growth index (worst 0–100 best)	72.9	2023	●	●	Press Freedom Index (worst 0–100 best)	33.0	2025	●	↓	
Victims of modern slavery (per 1,000 population)	8.0	2022	●	●	Access to and affordability of justice (worst 0–1 best)	0.43	2023	●	→	
Adults with an account at a bank or other financial institution or with a mobile-money-service provider (% of population aged 15 or over)	77.5	2021	●	↑	Timeliness of administrative proceedings (worst 0–1 best)	0.39	2023	●	→	
Unemployment rate (% of total labor force, ages 15+)	4.2	2025	●	↑	Expropriations are lawful and adequately compensated (worst 0–1 best)	0.63	2023	●	↓	
Fundamental labor rights are effectively guaranteed (worst 0–1 best)	0.51	2023	●	↗	SDG17 – Partnerships for the Goals					
Fatal work-related accidents embodied in imports (per million population)	0.1	2018	●	→	Government spending on health and education (% of GDP)	5.4	2022	●	→	
Victims of modern slavery embodied in imports (per 100,000 population)	3.1	2018	●	●	For high-income and all OECD DAC countries: International concessional public finance, including official development assistance (% of GNI)	●	●	●	●	
					Other countries: Government revenue excluding grants (% of GDP)	9.1	2022	●	↓	
					Corporate Tax Haven Score (best 0–100 worst)	*	0	2024	●	●
					Shifted profits of multinationals (US\$ billion)	*	0.0	2021	●	●
					Statistical Performance Index (worst 0–100 best)	73.6	2023	●	↑	
					Index of countries' support to UN-based multilateralism (worst 0–100 best)	63.8	2025	●	●	

* Imputed data point, ** Not applicable
NA = Data not available